

Muslim Women's Practical Role In Establishment Of Social Non-Violence

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
August 10, 2021

Accepted:
March 11, 2022

Keywords :

Essential, Femininity,
Spheres, Abstention And
Destination

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6348099

Abstract

Today, the world can become heaven when both the forces of men and women operate peacefully under the universe are engaged in their own respective spheres which provide the life vehicle ease in reaching the destination. No doubt, nonviolence is a personal practice of not causing harm to anyone under every condition. It may come from the belief that hurting people, animals or the environment is unnecessary to achieve an outcome and it may refer to a general philosophy of abstention from violence. As, the feminist part is called a spinal cord of society, if they come forward in this field to improve the work for peace, the destination of our society will be closer. And then, in reality, the society will become a practical model of peace. Hence it can be called a peaceful society. This article aims to highlight the practical role of Muslim women in establishing non-violence and its social impacts through systematic studies and training.

Introduction

Violence against women is one such worst act which is not allowed by any society or religion. Almost in all the countries of the world, women are victims of violence. More than half of the population of the world consists of women but still this group is deprived of their basic rights. This critical condition is very pitiable. That's why social violence against women is increasing day by day. Different gatherings, conferences, seminars and meetings are held all over the world regarding violence against women. It was started in 1990 and its slogan was "Peace at home and peace in the world". A few years ago, on the 25th anniversary of this movement, Silver Jubilee was celebrated all over the world. Therefore, the international day for the promotion of non-violence is celebrated around the world on March 8th. Celebrating this, day aims to raise awareness to end violence against them and establish Non-violence in society.

The literal meaning of violence:

Violence literally means oppression and abuse.

Terminological meaning of violence and Non-violence:

This term refers that by force imposition of one's point of view on others and the pursuit of some goal, individually or collectively, harms one's life, property and reputation. On the contrary, non-violence means presenting one's point of view with arguments and using peaceful means to achieve the desired goal.

Undoubtedly, the human history is witnessed that solid social success can only be achieved through non-violence, while the change brought by violence is never lasting, because the principle of non-violence is accordance with human life. Even if through it, sometimes no particular goal is achieved, at least it does not spread social corruption and instability. This is Islamic teaching that people should be persuaded only through non-violence and no such step should be taken before obtaining legal authority.

The Qur'an has drawn attention towards this fact at many places. That's why during the Makah period, the Holy Prophet (PBUH) and his Companions were oppressed so much but no violent action was ever taken by the believers in these difficult circumstances.

Explanation violence and non-violence

Non-violence never necessarily means encouraging wrongdoing, but it means challenging law peacefully, in such a way that cannot implemented by any tribe, government or state. Non-violence is not the name of any specific timely strategy or policy, but it is the name of an everlasting principle and mentality. The principle of non-violence leads a society to the goodness because it is the flag bearer of peace & reform and the forerunner of progress.

But this principle also requires man's patience. On the contrary, violent action, which is a based on haste and emotions, causes remorse and regret for humanity. That's why Allah Almighty has instructed man to be patient and perseverance because patience is the name of such a mentality and mental attitude in which man submits his emotions according to the command of Allah Almighty. Hence, the Holy Qur'an has asked about patience at about 130 places. This means that when the circumstances are unfavorable for a person, he should not lose heart, but he should believe that Allah Almighty is watching all the circumstances and He will change the circumstances whenever He wants. Therefore, a Muslim with a cool heart and mind should work, avoid

panic and frustration, carefully consider all the circumstances again, formulate a peaceful strategy and follow it steadfastly, because only with the weapon of non-violence, we can win today's battle and turn the tide in our favor, because social peace can be established only through mutual love & understanding

No doubt, establishment of peace and mutual love go side by side from the beginning, so they are inseparable from each other. That is to say, when there is mutual love between the society members, it is promoted, then society will inevitably be peaceful and only then solid social peace can be possibly established.

Otherwise a society of unrest and chaos will be established which will rapidly run towards decline. Therefore, for peace prevailing in any society, mutual love among humans is essential. At the time of the establishment of the Islamic society, this instruction of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) was in the view of the Companions and the Shaba's, about which Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal has mentioned in his Musnad Ahmed as:

“It is narrated from a sheikh of Banu Sulait that once I came in the service of the Holy Prophet (PBUH), at that time the Holy Prophet (PBUH) was sitting and the people surrounded him in a circle. The Prophet (PBUH) was wearing a thick apron and he (PBUH) was pointing with his fingers. I heard, he said that a Muslim is the brother of another Muslim; he does not oppress him and does not leave him helpless. Piety is place here. Piety is place here, that is, in the heart. And those who love others for the sake of Allah, nothing can separate them except the new thing which one of them invents, and the one who invents something is evil (said three times)” .

Therefore, by following this command, Muslim women used to help others in their troubles and anxiety, and in addition, help their neighbors in every possible way. The Companions, following the Sunnah of the Prophet (PBUH), used to go to women's homes and take care of them. They used to talk healthily things and visit the sick in every possible way. Once, a Suffa companion was ill, Umme- Darda came on a camel; she visited him, enquired about his health and encouraged him. In *Al-Adab Al-Mufrid*, Imam Bukhari has narrated this incident as:

“Isaw Umm al-Darda on her mound sticks that had no family members on him, belonging to a man from the people of the mosque from the Ansar.”

Undoubtedly, the Companions loved their children very much, although this peculiar attribute was generally found in all the companions, but the women of Quraish were especially distinguished in the mentioned matter. So, the Holy Prophet (PBUH) himself praised them for this feature thus:

“The Qurayshi women are better than all the other women who ride camels, because they are the ones who love their children the most and protect their husband's property” .ⁱ

Therefore, along with other qualities, another virtue that was present in the Companions was that whenever they saw someone in trouble or distress, they would immediately come to his help. Hazrat Asma Bint Abu Bakr had also such an incident where she did not know how to bake bread, her neighbors used to bake bread for her. As stated in *Sahih Muslim* as:

“It is narrated by Hazrat Asma Bint Abu Bakr that Hazrat Zubair Bin Al-Awwam married me, when he had no land, no wealth, and no servant and nothing except a horse, I used to feed his horse, look after and serve it on his behalf. I used to dig nuts for his horse, feed it grass and water. I used to draw water from buckets, my Ansari neighbors used to bake bread for me and they were very pious women” .

Thus, it is clear from this extract that in the first century AH, the Muslim women supported each other in their domestic affairs and had regular mutual interactions.

In this regard, Bukhari Sharif has mentioned it thus:

“Umm e Alaa, an Ansari woman narrated, who had pledged allegiance to the Holy Prophet (PBUH), said that the migrants had drawn lot for the division of the Ansar and Othman Bin Mazoon came to our part. We took him at our house and he fell ill and died. He was given bath and shrouded then the Holy Prophet (PBUH) also visited him. I said: O Abu al-Sa'ib, may Allah's mercy on you! My witness about you is that Allah has made you dignified” .

The Muslim women truly followed the teachings of the Prophet (PBUH); therefore the female companions performed human rights in a good way. Hazrat Zainab (R.A) was married to Abul Aas, who was in the state of disbelief at that time and the battle of Badar took place and he was captured. The Prophet (PBUH) wanted to release the war captives, in the ransom of Abul Aas; Hazrat Zainab (RA) sent the commemorative necklace which Hazrat Khadija (RA) had given her at the time of her marriage. Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal narrates this incident in this regard:

“It is narrated by Hazrat Ayesha (RA) that when the people of Makah sent ransom for their captives, (her daughter) Hazrat Zainab (RA) sent wealth for

the ransom of her husband (Abul Aas), in which there was a necklace which she had received from her mother Hazrat Khadija (R.A.)”

Thus, this incident clearly shows that in the primitive Islam, women used to take great care of their husbands, by sacrificing valuable goods, things and even precious necklaces for their release. Rather, Islam has provided women an ample space for their practical activities. Just as they can advance in the path of knowledge and literature, they are also allowed to pursue various professions and perform different national and services for social peace.

Of course, men are primarily responsible for earning livelihood, but depending on the requirements and circumstances, if this responsibility falls on women as well, then Islam does not forbid it as it is commanded.

“For men, there is a share according to their earnings and for women there is a share according to their own earnings”.

This verse clears that Islam wants women able to face the hardships of life with courage and perseverance. Hence, for this motive, Sharia has taught women to live a simple and hard life. Therefore, the Muslim women have participated in peace and reform activities abiding by Sharia the rules and regulations when required. Some prominent examples of them are as follows:

Hazrat Abdullah bin Masood’s wife (Zainab) was familiar with domestic industry and craft, through which she used to meet the expenses of her children and family. One day, she came to the Holy Prophet (PBUH) and asked about spending on her husband. Ibn e Athir has mentioned it thus:

“I am an artisan woman, I make and sell things (that’s why I can make money) but my husband and children have no other source of income because they have nothing”.

She asked such if she can spend on her husband. He (PBUH) replied, "Yes, you will also get its reward." Another such incident is that of Hazrat Khola Bint Tha'laba, her husband once unintentionally said that from today your status is like that of my mother. She said, "By God, you have said a very big thing. I don't know what will be its result? Then they came to the Holy Prophet (PBUH) to ask about the problem and told the matter.

The Prophet (PBUH) asked her husband, “What does your cousin's daughter say?” He says, she is right; I have expressed my condolences to her and declared her as my mother's back. Since no saying of Allah on this issue had been revealed at that time, the Holy Prophet (PBUH) said: Stay away from your wife till any order is issued in this regard. Ibn e Sa'ad narrated the answer of Hazrat Khola as:

“O, Messenger of Allah, he has nothing to spend on, I spend on him and then how can he live apart from me”?

The above narrated quotations show how much women loved their family members and asked they can earn and spend money on their husbands and children as well.

Ibn Hajar Asqalani narrates the incident of Hazrat Umm e Hakim Bint Al-Harith who was married to Ikrimah Ibn Abi Jahal that she herself embraced Islam on the day of the conquest of Makkah but her husband fled to Yemen. Hazrat Umm Hakim traveled to Yemen and invited him towards Islam. He embraced Islam and came to the Holy Prophet (PBUH).

It seems that the love and devotion with which the Muslim women performed the duty of preaching the religion is enviable and can be written in golden letters. Similarly, Ibn Abdul Bar mentioned it in Al-Isti'ab.

“And she asked the Prophet (PBUH) for peace and she was granted peace to her husband, Ikrimah, but Ikrimah had fled to Yemen, and she went out to seek him, and she returned him until he embraced Islam, and they were matched together for their marriage”.

The above quoted extracts clearly show that Umm e Hakim not only embraced Islam but also attracted her husband to Islam. On the other hand, she asked permission from the Holy Prophet and sought peace. Therefore, the woman’s status was so high that at the request of a woman, he (PBUH) not only allowed Ikrimah but also gave orders of refuge. Thus a woman played her ideal peaceful role in preventing sedition and social non-violence.

It is a general rule, if one's opponent gets into trouble; there is no better chance of revenge. But the Prophet did not leave any space for hatred and revenge in the companion’s hearts. Hazrat Ayesha (AS) and Hazrat Zainab (AS) sometimes happened to a bit quarrel with each other, but when Hazrat Ayesha (AS) was slandered and the Holy Prophet (SAW) inquired about from Hazrat Zainab (AS) her moral condition, instead of taking revenge, she said: I protect my eyes completely; I know nothing but goodness towards her. Revenge is a big thing; they did not like to hate their opponent, that’s why they were well aware of the virtues of forgiving for the sake of Allah Almighty.

Summary Discussion:

The contemporary modern tragedy is that man is always looking for lame excuses for violence against women. In our society, even if the wife is given less dowry, she would be victim of violence. Sometimes they have to face coercion for demanding the right of education and sometimes they are killed in the name of honor

for marrying of their own choice. Even, laws are present regarding the above atrocities but they are not implemented accordingly. Now, there is a dire need to end violence against women. We have to work on different aspects and levels for its eradication. This includes strict legislation against violence on females, its implementation, the abolishment of outdated customs, the rights to a marriage of choice along with arrange marriage, the empowerment of women economically and the elimination of evils such as dowry and other issues, as social violence has many negative effects on women. Through daily newspapers and magazines, incidents of burning, beatings and severe injuries pass before our eyes in the kind of abuse where women are injured or killed. Some of the negative effects of violence on women's lives are nervous stress, remorse and confusion, a state of uncertainty, lack of enthusiasm & confidence and the attitude of the abusive man.

Such men should consult regularly to some expert psychologist so that they can control their habits and re-establish a comfortable & peaceful home environment. By becoming useful citizens, they can play their peculiar positive role in the social peace and reform with whole heartedly.

The government should take suitable steps for the eradication of violence against women and include solutions to women's issues in its priorities. Because if there is violence against half the population of our country; then, how social peace can be established without ending oppression and violence against women, it is necessary to provide them timely cheap justice. Unless the culprit is punished, the system will not be reformed. Non-violence's effects against women will be that social oppression and lawlessness will end and only then the foundation of love and affection can be laid and the country will be run on the path of development. Although this journey to end violence against women and to make them active and independent members of society is very long, but if it is taken seriously and responsibly, women can be protected from violence, so that they can play their positive role without fear for social peace and reform.

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